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“JOB MISMATCH AND CAREER MISALIGNMENT AMONG EDUCATION GRADUATES IN THE PHILIPPINES”

Have you ever observed how many education graduates ends up working in another job and not base in their educational degree? Instead of teaching, a lot of them are now in offices, banks, BPO companies, or customer service jobs. It's something I've seen happen often, and honestly, it raises a lot of questions about whether the system is really working for graduates. One example that stuck with me is my cousin. She graduated with honors, passed the board exam, and spent months applying to schools. She also attended interviews, and submitted documents repeatedly, and waited for patiently opportunities but had that never came. Eventually, she accepted a job as an administrative assistant because she needed an income. Now, she rarely uses what she studied in college. Stories like hers are becoming more common among Education graduates in the Philippines. The problem is not that Education graduates are unqualified or lazy. In reality, many of them are hardworking and capable. The issue is that there are simply not enough teaching positions available compared to the growing number of graduates every year.

Education students spend four years learning lesson planning, classroom management, teaching strategies, and child development. Those skills are important and valuable, especially for those who truly want to become teachers. However, when thousands of graduates compete for limited openings, many are left without a chance to practice the profession. Another reason why graduates struggle is because some parts of the curriculum no longer match the demands of today's job market. Most Education programs focus heavily on theories and classroom instruction, but they give little attention to skills that are useful in other industries. For example, many companies now look for applicants with knowledge in digital tools, office software, data management, and professional communication. Graduates from Business, IT, or Communication programs usually have an advantage in these areas. Meanwhile, Education graduates often feel unprepared when applying for non-teaching jobs because they were not trained for those kinds of tasks during college. Because of this, some graduates begin to wonder whether their education prepared them for enough career options outside teaching. Underemployment is another reality many graduates experience. Some end up in jobs that do not fully use their degree or professional skills. I know someone who majored in English and wanted to become a teacher or editor. Unfortunately, schools did not hire her, and publishing companies required experience she did not have. In the end, she worked in customer service instead. She performs well in her job because she communicates clearly and handles people professionally, but she still feels disappointed that her years of study are not being fully utilized. Situations like this are common and can make graduates feel that their efforts and sacrifices were wasted.

Salary is also a major factor. Public school positions usually offer better stability and benefits, but openings are limited and the hiring process can take a long time. On the other hand, many private schools offer low starting salaries that are barely enough for transportation, meals, and daily expenses. Because of this, some graduates choose office or BPO jobs that offer higher pay and more immediate financial support. For many graduates, it is not about losing passion for teaching. It is about practicality and survival. Many families still believe that finishing college automatically guarantees stable employment. Education, in particular, is often viewed as a secure career choice. Because of these expectations, students enter the program believing they will easily find work after graduation. However, reality is often very different. After earning their degrees and licenses, many graduates discover that opportunities are limited. Some are forced to shift careers, while others feel uncertain about their future. This gap between expectations and reality creates frustration and disappointment. Despite these challenges, Education graduates still possess valuable skills. They are trained to communicate effectively, organize tasks, lead groups, and work patiently with others. These are strengths that can be useful in many industries. The problem is that schools rarely guide students on how to apply these abilities outside the teaching profession.

Job mismatch and career misalignment remain serious issues among Education graduates in the Philippines. Limited teaching positions, outdated curricula, low salaries, and lack of practical training push many graduates into careers unrelated to their field of study. Although Education graduates have strong transferable skills, many are not given enough opportunities or preparation to use them effectively in other industries. Because of this, graduates often feel frustrated and uncertain about their career paths after years of hard work and study. To improve this situation, colleges and universities should update their curricula, provide additional practical training, and offer realistic career guidance. Graduates should be prepared not only for teaching but also for other professional opportunities where their skills can be valuable

